

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION, FIRE DETECTION AND ALARM SYSTEM, AND CLOSED-CIRCUIT TELEVISION (CCTV) SYSTEM TRAINER

Emil Joey B. Turqueza ¹ and Jomel R. Angangan, MTE ²

¹ *Isabela School of Arts and Trades, Department of Education, City of Ilagan, Isabela, Philippines*

² *Isabela State University-City of Ilagan Campus, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11311248>

ABSTRACT

This study aimed at the development and evaluation of an Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) System Trainer. Employing a developmental research method, the trainer was designed, constructed, assembled, tested, revised, and reassembled for functionality. A descriptive-evaluative approach was used to assess its acceptability and functionality, utilizing questionnaire checklists, unstructured interviews, and observations. Respondents included fifty industry experts and thirty-five instructors from various Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) schools and firms in Ilagan, Isabela. The evaluation revealed strong consensus on the trainer's design, durability, functionality, instructional applicability, and safety, with mean scores of 4.972 and 4.983 from instructors and experts, respectively. No significant differences were found between the two groups' evaluations. Recommendations for enhancement included integrating solar input, improving portability with lightweight materials, providing comprehensive instructional resources, updating safety features, incorporating a dust protection curtain, and developing a version suitable for outdoor use. These enhancements aim to align the trainer with industry trends, promote sustainability, and ensure a safe, versatile, and effective training tool. The study concludes that the trainer is highly effective in improving practical skills, with valuable insights for future improvements.

Keywords: *Electrical Installation, Fire Detection, Alarm System, CCTV System, Trainer Development, Vocational Training, System Evaluation.*

INTRODUCTION

Vocational education is important in shaping a workforce that meets the dynamic demands of the industrial sector. It requires a robust learning model that emphasizes mastery of specific competencies tailored to industry needs. One effective approach to achieving this is through the integration of practical training facilities, such as mock-up trainers, into the educational framework. These trainers serve as instrumental tools in bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, providing students with hands-on experience in real-world scenarios.

The Philippines, renowned for its skilled workforce, faces the challenge of sustaining its competitiveness in the global market. As globalization opens doors to a diverse workforce, it becomes imperative for the Philippines to elevate its standards and compete on a global scale. To achieve this, the quality of vocational education and training must be assessed and enhanced.

A critical aspect of vocational education is the availability of training facilities and instructional equipment. In the realm of technology courses, such as electrical training, the need for well-equipped laboratories and workshops is particularly significant. These facilities not only facilitate the teaching-learning process but also ensure that graduates are equipped with the standard skills required by industries.

However, the education sector in the Philippines grapples with challenges, including the scarcity of training equipment in laboratories and workshops. The rapid pace of technological advancement further exacerbates this issue, necessitating the adaptation of educational resources to keep pace with industry requirements. As industries embrace automation and technological innovation, there is a growing demand for skilled workers proficient in new technologies.

In response to these challenges, researchers have embarked on endeavors to develop and evaluate instructional trainers tailored to meet industry standards. A plethora of studies have explored various aspects of instructional trainers in electrical engineering and related fields. Pereyra (2020) emphasizes the importance of mock-up trainers in developing technical skills in wiring installation, while Tejano (2018) focuses on the efficacy of an Industrial Motor Control System Trainer in TVET programs. Similarly, Hamid et al. (2020) and Elfizon et al. (2019) delve into the development of electric circuit trainers, highlighting their feasibility and effectiveness in practical learning.

Moreover, studies such as those by Munawi et.al (2020) and Laboga (2023) underscore the significance of hands-on experience in enhancing critical thinking skills and bridging the gap between theory and practice. Bartolome (2019) addresses the scarcity of industrial equipment in teaching electrical technology subjects and proposes solutions to enhance instructional applicability. Additionally, Angangan (2021) and Rosales (2022) assess the acceptability and effectiveness of instructional trainers in preparing students for industry certifications.

Furthermore, advancements in technology have led to the development of innovative instructional trainers, as demonstrated by studies such as those by Mikhail and Alavizadeh (2019) and Sarasar (2024). These trainers, ranging from portable programmable logic controllers to basic fire alarm circuits, cater to diverse educational needs and underscore the importance of practical training in vocational education.

In light of these insights, this research aims to contribute to the advancement of vocational education by developing and evaluating an integrated Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer. By leveraging insights from previous studies and addressing practical needs, this integrated trainer seeks to enhance the technical skills of learners in electrical majors, preparing them to meet industry standards and certifications. Through a comprehensive review of related literature and studies, this research aims to provide a holistic understanding of the challenges and opportunities in technical vocational education, laying the groundwork for the development of effective instructional trainers aligned with industry requirements.

Research Questions

The primary goal of this study was to develop and evaluate Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer as teaching equipment for Electrical Engineering, Electrical Technology, Electrical Installation and Maintenance EIM, Senior High School TVL track students, industry workers, and for training in preparation for Electrical Installation and Maintenance NC II Assessment.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the processes involved in designing and developing an Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer?
2. What laboratory activities could be performed using the Developed Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer?
3. What is the evaluation of the electrical instructors/teachers and electrical industry experts on the developed Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer in the following criteria:
 - a. design and durability
 - b. functionality
 - c. instructional applicability
 - d. safety
4. Is there a significant difference in the evaluations of the respondents on the level of acceptability of the Developed Electrical Installation, Fire Detection, Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer in terms of the aforementioned criteria?
5. What further improvement can be done on the Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer?

METHODOLOGY

This research study employed the developmental method where the researcher conceptualized the design, construction, and specification of the developed Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer. In this study, the trainer was designed, constructed, and assembled in conformity with the design. Then the revision followed any problems or defects and was reassembled until it was found functional.

Furthermore, the study utilized descriptive-evaluative research. The main data-gathering instrument used was a set of questionnaire checklists supplemented by unstructured interviews and observation.

Source of Data

The respondents of the study were fifty (50) Industry Experts and thirty-five (35) teachers/instructors. The teachers/instructors were from the different TVET schools in the City of Ilagan, Isabela while the industry experts were from different firms. These respondents had to complete an evaluation form that determines the acceptability and functionality of the trainer.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the researcher evaluated the project, a formal request to the target respondents through their respective general managers, supervisors, principals, and executive officers. The letter was sent to different schools, electrical shops, and other establishments with maintenance electricians who are experts in the electrical industry.

When granted, the researcher floated the survey questionnaire from one school to another. The same process was also employed with different firms.

Data Gathering Instrument

The researcher used the evaluation questionnaires from the study of Angangan (2021) of Isabela State University-City of Ilagan entitled "Construction and Evaluation of Manually-Operated and Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) Ready Motor Control Trainer" and from the study of Bartolome (2019) of Isabela School of Arts and trades-Technical education Skills Development Authority Isabela entitled "Industrial Motor Control System trainer". The instrument consisted of criteria for evaluating the general acceptability of the developed electrical trainer in terms of *Design and Durability, Functionality, Instructional Applicability, and Safety*.

The 5 point Likert Scale was used in the evaluation as shown below.

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
4	3.50-4.49	Agree (A)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Agree (MA)
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree (D)
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree (SD)

The needed data were obtained from Electrical Teachers/ TVET Trainers/ Electrical Instructors, and Industry Expert. The researcher conducted actual testing of the trainer for the project evaluation of the respondents and retrieved the questionnaire checklist from the respondents.

The data gathered from electrical teachers and Industry experts were analyzed and interpreted. The recommendations and suggestions of the respondents were considered for the improvement of the trainer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Product Design and Development

The following tables show the materials used (with their costs) in the development of the Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer.

Table 1. Bill of Materials for Frame and Board Assembly

Item No.	Qty.	Unit	Item/Description	Unit Price	Total Price
1	1	Pcs.	Square steel tubing, $\frac{3}{4}$ " x $\frac{3}{4}$ " x 18', S-40	250.00	250.00
2	3	Pcs	Square steel tubing, 1"x 1"x 18', S-40	350.00	1,050.00
3	3	Pcs.	Rectangular steel tubing, 1"x 2"x18', S-40	650.00	1,950.00
4	2	Kg	Welding Rod, 6011	80.00	160.00
5	4	Pcs.	$\frac{1}{2}$ " Marine Plywood	630.00	2,520.00

6	4	Pcs.	Swivel Caster Wheel	150.00	600.00
7	150	Pcs.	1" Metal Black Screw	1.00	150.00
8	1	Pcs	Grinding Disk	30.00	30.00
9	3	Pcs	Cutting Disk	30.00	90.00
			Sub – Total		6,800.00

Table 2. Bill of Materials for Painting

Item No.	Qty.	Unit	Item/Description	Unit Price	Total Price
1	5	Pads	Sandpaper, # 100, # 240	50.00	250.00
2	1	Pcs.	Body filler	180.00	180.00
3	1	Gallon	Wall putty	480.00	480.00
4	4	Pcs	Primer spray paint, gray 400 cc	100.00	400.00
5	1	Gal	White paint	480.00	480.00
			Sub – Total		1,790.00

Table 3. Bill of Electrical Materials/Supplies

Item No.	Qty.	Unit	Item/Description	Unit Price	Total Price
1	1	Set	4 Zone Fire Detection and Alarm System	17,000.00	17,000.00
2	1	Set	4 Channel Close Circuit Television	13,000.00	13,000.00
3	3	Pcs	Circuit Breaker 10 A, 2 pole Din rail type	180.00	540.00
4	9	Pcs	2x2 Lamp Holder	30.00	270.00
5	1	Set	MTS panel board	1,500.00	1,500.00
6	3	Pcs	Pilot Light Indicator 220v	25.00	75.00
7	1	Pc	4 Holes Panel Board	750.00	750.00
8	1	Pc	Circuit Breaker 40A Plug-in type	350.00	350.00
9	1	Pc	Circuit Breaker 30A Plug-in type	350.00	350.00
10	1	Pc	Circuit Breaker 20A Plug-in type	350.00	350.00
11	1	Pc	Circuit Breaker 15A Plug-in type	350.00	350.00
12	1	Pc	Round Meter Base ¾" hole	300.00	300.00
13	1	Set	Flash type Switches 1gang	120.00	120.00
14	1	Set	Flash type Switches 2gang	150.00	150.00
15	1	Set	Flash type Switches 3gang	180.00	180.00
16	2	Set	Flash type Switches 3-way	160.00	160.00
17	1	Set	Flash type Switches 4-way	800.00	800.00

18	3	Sets	Flash type Convenience Outlet 2gang	160.00	160.00
19	1	Set	GFCI outlet	800.00	800.00
20	3	set	1 hole panel board	180.00	540.00
21	8	Pcs	300x300x1m slotted cable ducks	100.00	800.00
22	4	pcs	½" Pipe Connector	20.00	80.00
23	1	Pc	¾" Entrance Cup	50.00	50.00
24	75	mts	2.0 mm2 THHN Wire	20	1,500.00
25	15	mts	3.5 mm2 THHN Wire	15	450.00
26	60	Pcs	Binding post	10	600.00
27	60	pcs	Banana Plug	5	300.00
28	250	pc	½' EMT Pipe	250	250.00
29	3	pcs	Button Box, 1 hole, 22mm dia.	50	150.00
30	75	Mts	TF wire #16	20	1,125.00
31	50	Pcs	1' Black screw	1	50.00
			Sub – Total		P51,690.00

Tools and Equipment Used

Table 4. Tools and equipment used in developing the trainer

Welding Machine	crosscut saw
Hack	Drill bit
Air compressors	Bar level
Electric drills	Pull-push rule/steel rule
Angle grinder	Pliers
Claw hammer	L-square
Screwdriver	

Design and Layout

Creating the layout for the Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer involved formulating the design concept, preparing drawings, and developing project plans. The researcher's expertise and experiences were instrumental in shaping the trainer's design. By conceptualizing the structure, producing detailed drawings, and outlining project plans, the trainer could be effectively tailored to meet the training program's objectives. It was essential to ensure that the design encompassed all necessary elements to provide a realistic and practical learning environment for trainees/learners.

The trainer's design and layout showcased the researcher's knowledge and skills in the field, aiming to optimize the training program's impact.

Figure 1. Drawings of the Proposed Trainer

Construction of the electrical installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Close-Circuit Television system trainer

The construction project entails developing a training setup focused on Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System. Key considerations include ensuring that the trainer is tailored to the comprehension level of Senior High School EIM NC II students, Electrical Technology learners, TVET instructors, and industry experts. It operates manually and relies on a 230V AC, 60-hertz power source while prioritizing environmental sustainability. The trainer is intended to skillfully train and advance industry professionals for EIM NC II certification. Moreover, the project aims to utilize locally and commercially available materials and supplies, emphasizing practicality and accessibility in its construction.

The following procedures were taken to develop the various components of the trainer:

1. Gathering tools, equipment, and materials required for the project.
2. Creating the steel frame based on the project's drawings and designs.
3. Welding and cutting plywood to the specified dimensions.
4. Painting the plywood and attaching it to the frame.
5. Installing various devices on the trainer.
6. Testing and commissioning the trainer, recording observations, corrections, and modifications.
7. Revising and modifying the trainer based on test results to enhance its performance and fix any diagnostic errors.

Figure 2. The researcher assembles the frame of the trainer, carefully following the measurement.

Figure 4. Installing various devices to the trainer

Figure 5. Testing and commissioning the trainer

Figure 6. The Developed Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer

Laboratory Activities That Could be Performed Using the Developed Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer

Below are the laboratory activities that can be performed using the developed EIFDASCCTV System Trainer:

A. Electrical Installation

1. Kilo-watt hour meter.
2. Manual transfer switch.
3. Manual transfer switch normal and emergency power connection.
4. Distribution panel board.
5. Circuit breaker ampacity and termination.
6. Convenience outlet connection.
7. Ground fault current interrupter.
8. 1 bulb controlled by 1-S1.
9. 2 bulbs controlled by 2-S1 in one location.
10. 3 bulbs controlled by 3-S1 in one location.
11. 3 bulbs controlled by 3-S1 in three locations.
12. 4 bulbs controlled alternately by 2-S1 in one location.
13. 1 bulb controlled by 2-S3W in two locations.
14. 2 bulbs controlled by 2-S3W in two locations.
15. 1 bulb controlled by 2-S3W and 1-S4W in three locations.
16. 2 bulbs controlled by 2-S3W and 1-S4W in three locations.
17. 3 bulbs controlled by 3-S1 in three different locations.
18. Grounding system installation.

B. Fire Detection and Alarm System

1. Heat detector
2. Smoke detector
3. Bell connection
4. Manual call point polarity
5. Sounder polarity
6. Fire alarm control panel termination
7. Battery connection
8. AC and DC input power supply

C. Close-Circuit Television

1. Camera DC and video input
2. TV monitor AC supply and VGA
3. DVR output and DC power supply
4. Centralize power supply output and termination

Level of Acceptability of the developed Electrical Installation, Fire and Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer

The respondents' evaluation of the acceptability of the developed Electrical Installation, Fire and Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer is shown in Table 5 below.

Table 5. Level of acceptability of the developed electrical installation, fire detection, and alarm system, and closed-circuit television system trainer as perceived by respondents in terms of design and durability, functionality, instructional applicability, and safety

Respondents	Criteria	Mean	Description
Electrical Instructors/Teachers	<i>Design and Durability</i>	4.937	Strongly Agree
	1. The trainer is both distinctive and long-lasting.	4.97	Strongly Agree
	2. The trainer can be readily replicated for student use.	4.914	Strongly Agree
	3. The trainer is made out of well-assembled and locally available components.	5.00	Strongly Agree
	4. The trainer's components are sturdy and can withstand tension.	4.89	Strongly Agree
	5. The trainer can stay strong and in good condition for the period uses.	4.937	Strongly Agree
	<i>Functionality</i>	4.980	Strongly Agree
	1. The trainer can serve its purpose effectively and efficiently.	4.971	Strongly Agree
	2. The trainer demonstrates an actual operation for instructional purposes.	4.943	Strongly Agree
	3. The trainer is simple to use and care for.	5.00	Strongly Agree
	4. All of the trainer's components are fully working.	4.971	Strongly Agree
	5. The trainer is simple to operate and manipulate.	5.00	Strongly Agree
	<i>Instructional Applicability</i>	4.971	Strongly Agree
	1. The trainer can be used to improve skills.	4.900	Strongly Agree
	2. The trainer is effective when it comes to instructional materials and workshop utilization.	5.00	Strongly Agree
	3. Students, industry experts, trainers/teachers, and others can use the trainer.	4.943	Strongly Agree

	4. The trainer can improve the training and teaching-learning processes.	5.00	Strongly Agree
	5. The trainer can be used for training in competency assessment in EIM NC II.	4.971	Strongly Agree
	Safety	5.00	Strongly Agree
	1. The trainer is outfitted with safety and protection features.	5.00	Strongly Agree
	2. All trainer elements and components are securely secured for safety.	5.00	Strongly Agree
	3. The trainer's components are installed on non-conductor material.	5.00	Strongly Agree
	4. The trainer is outfitted with a grounding system to ensure the user's safety	5.00	Strongly Agree
	5. The trainer is both safe and user-friendly.	5.00	Strongly Agree
	Overall Mean	4.972	Strongly Agree
Industry Experts	Design and Durability	4.956	Strongly Agree
	1. The trainer is both distinctive and long-lasting.	4.900	Strongly Agree
	2. The trainer can be readily replicated for student use.	5.00	Strongly Agree
	3. The trainer is made out of well-assembled and locally available components.	4.980	Strongly Agree
	4. The trainer's components are sturdy and can withstand tension.	4.940	Strongly Agree
	5. The trainer can stay strong and in good condition for the period uses.	4.960	Strongly Agree
	Functionality	4.990	Strongly Agree
	1. The trainer can serve its purpose effectively and efficiently.	4.980	Strongly Agree
	2. The trainer demonstrates an actual operation for instructional purposes.	5.00	Strongly Agree
	3. The trainer is simple to use and care for.	5.00	Strongly Agree
	4. All of the trainer's components are fully working.	5.00	Strongly Agree
	5. The trainer is simple to operate and manipulate.	4.960	Strongly Agree
	Instructional Applicability	4.988	Strongly Agree

1. The trainer can be used to improve skills.	5.00	
2. The trainer is effective when it comes to instructional materials and workshop utilization.	4.960	Strongly Agree
3. Students, industry experts, trainers/teachers, and others can use the trainer.	5.00	Strongly Agree
4. The trainer can improve the training and teaching-learning processes.	4.980	Strongly Agree
5. The trainer can be used for training in competency assessment in EIM NC II.	5.00	Strongly Agree
Safety	4.996	Strongly Agree
1. The trainer is outfitted with safety and protection features.	5.00	Strongly Agree
2. All trainer elements and components are securely secured for safety.	4.980	Strongly Agree
3. The trainer's components are installed on non-conductor material.	5.00	Strongly Agree
4. The trainer is outfitted with a grounding system to ensure the user's safety	5.00	Strongly Agree
5. The trainer is both safe and user-friendly.	5.00	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.983	Strongly Agree

It can be gleaned from the table that for both Electrical Instructors/Teachers and Industry Experts, in terms of Design and Durability, they evaluated it with a mean of 4.937 and 4.956, respectively. This indicates a high level of agreement among Electrical Instructors/Teachers regarding the design and durability of the system. They strongly agreed that the design is robust and durable.

As to the Functionality, the respondents gave a mean of 4.980 and 4.990, respectively. Both groups of respondents strongly agreed that the system functions effectively according to its intended purpose. This indicates that they find the trainer highly effective and efficient in performing its intended functions. It suggests that the trainer meets or exceeds their expectations in terms of performance and usability.

Concerning its Instructional Applicability, the respondents rated the developed trainer with a mean of 4.971 and 4.988, respectively. There was strong agreement that the system is highly applicable for instructional purposes, suggesting that it aligns well with the teaching objectives. This implies that they believe that the trainer is highly suitable

and relevant for instructional purposes, indicating that it effectively supports their teaching objectives and methods.

Regarding the Safety of the developed product, both groups of respondents gave a mean of 5.00 and 4.996, respectively. Both groups have unanimous agreement among Electrical Instructors/Teachers and Industry Experts that the system is safe to use, which is a crucial aspect, especially in educational settings. This suggests that they perceive the trainer to be extremely safe to use, implying that it meets or exceeds safety standards and regulations.

In summary, both groups, Electrical Instructors/Teachers and Industry Experts, highly approved of the developed Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer. The system is perceived as robust, functional, applicable for instructional purposes, and importantly, safe. This high level of acceptability suggests that the system is well-designed and meets the needs and expectations of both educators and industry professionals.

Comparison in the Evaluations of the Respondents on the Level of Acceptability of the Developed Electrical Installation, Fire Detection, Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer

Table 6. Comparison in the evaluation of the respondents on the developed Electrical Installation, Fire Detection, and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer

Respondents	Criteria	F-Value	p-Value	Decision	Remarks
Electrical Instructors/Teachers	Design and Durability	0.6867	0.4097	Accept H_0	Not Significant
	Functionality	0.7914	0.3762	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Industry Experts	Instructional Applicability	1.6509	0.2024	Accept H_0	Not Significant
	Safety	0.6975	0.4060	Accept H_0	Not Significant

The table exhibits the comparison in the evaluation of the developed Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer between two groups of respondents: Electrical Instructors/Teachers and Industry Experts. The analysis is based on four criteria: Design and Durability, Functionality, Instructional Applicability, and Safety. Each criterion's evaluation includes the F-value, p-value, decision, and remarks.

As shown in the table, for *Design and Durability*, F-Value = 0.6867 and p-Value = 0.4097 suggests the acceptance of the null hypothesis (H_0). The comparison of evaluation between Electrical Instructors/Teachers and Industry Experts regarding Design and

Durability shows a non-significant difference. This suggests that both groups have similar perceptions and evaluations regarding the design and durability of the system trainer.

In terms of its *functionality*, the F-Value = 0.7914 and p -Value = 0.3762, hence the H_0 is accepted. Similarly, there is no significant difference in the evaluation of Functionality between Electrical Instructors/Teachers and Industry Experts. Both groups perceive the functionality of the system trainer similarly.

Concerning its *Instructional Applicability*, an F-Value = 1.6509 and a p -Value = 0.2024 were computed. Therefore, accept H_0 . This indicates that there is no significant difference in the evaluation of Instructional Applicability between Electrical Instructors/Teachers and Industry Experts. Both groups agree on the system trainer's suitability for instructional purposes.

Lastly, for its *Safety*, F-Value = 0.6975 and p -Value = 0.4060. This means that the H_0 was accepted. Similar to the other criteria, there is no significant difference in the evaluation of Safety between Electrical Instructors/Teachers and Industry Experts. Both groups perceive the system trainer as equally safe.

Based on the results, the comparison analysis reveals that there were no significant differences in the evaluations between Electrical Instructors/Teachers and Industry Experts across all evaluated criteria. This suggests a consensus between the two groups regarding their perceptions of the developed system trainer's design, functionality, instructional applicability, and safety. The acceptance of the null hypothesis indicates that any observed differences in evaluations are likely due to chance rather than meaningful distinctions between the two groups.

Suggestions for Improvement for the Developed Electrical Installation, Fire Detection, Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer

For further improvement of the developed trainer, the following comments and suggestions were given by the respondents.

Comments:

- a. The trainer can operate easily with both teachers and students.
- b. The trainer is ready to use for enhancement training for teachers and electrical industry workers.
- c. The trainer is installed with a safety grounding system for the user.
- d. The connections are easy to follow.
- e. The trainer should use light materials for easy transport and carry.

Suggestions

- a. The trainer should incorporate solar input as an alternative source of power.
- b. The trainer should provide a curtain for dusty protection.

- c. The trainer is applicable only for indoor operations and training.
 - d. Before performing hands-on, the trainer should provide guidance.
 - e. The Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer are equipped with safety precautions.
 - f. An input timer should be placed/installed on the trainer to assess the trainee's speed during performance.
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Conclusions

In conclusion, the research study on the development and evaluation of the *Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer* demonstrates a systematic approach to creating a comprehensive training tool. The high levels of acceptability among both electrical instructors/teachers and industry experts, along with the consensus on the trainer's design and functionality, indicate its effectiveness in enhancing practical skills in the field. The identified areas for enhancement, such as incorporating renewable energy sources, improving portability, and enhancing safety features, offer valuable insights for further refining the trainer to meet the evolving needs of training programs. By implementing these suggestions, the trainer can evolve into a more versatile, user-friendly, and efficient tool, providing an enhanced training experience for individuals in the electrical industry.

Recommendations

Given the findings and conclusions above, the following are recommended:

1. To enhance the trainer's sustainability and provide exposure to renewable energy systems, integrating solar input as an alternative power source is recommended. This addition will align the trainer with current industry trends and promote environmental consciousness among trainees.
2. The trainer's portability should be enhanced by utilizing lightweight materials like aluminum or high-strength plastic composites will facilitate ease of transport and handling. This improvement will make the trainer more versatile and suitable for various training environments.
3. Pre-hands-on guidance through detailed instructional manuals, video tutorials, and interactive touchscreens should be offered to make sure that users understand the correct procedures and safety measures. Accessible resources will enhance the learning experience and promote safety awareness among trainees.
4. There should be regular updates to safety features, including emergency stop buttons and clear safety labels to further reduce risks and enhance user safety. Ensuring that the trainer meets the highest safety standards will create a secure learning environment for both students and industry professionals.

5. While the trainer is currently designed for indoor use, future iterations should be developed to withstand outdoor conditions. Highlighting this limitation and working towards creating a weather-resistant version will expand the trainer's usability in various training scenarios.

6. An input timer should be integrated to assess trainees' speed and efficiency which shall provide valuable performance data. This feature will help track progress, identify areas for improvement, and enhance the overall training effectiveness.

7. To ensure the trainer's longevity and operational efficiency, incorporating a dust protection curtain and implementing regular updates to safety features and protocols are essential. Maintenance protocols should be established to uphold the trainer's performance standards over time.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As the author of the research study *“Development and Evaluation of Electrical Installation, Fire Detection and Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television System Trainer”*, I affirm my unwavering commitment to upholding the highest ethical standards in research. Throughout the study, I ensured strict compliance with ethical guidelines, including obtaining informed consent from participants, guaranteeing their freedom to withdraw at any time, maintaining respondent anonymity, safeguarding their well-being, and avoiding conflicts of interest. I conducted the research with integrity, strictly avoiding plagiarism, ensuring unbiased interpretation of findings, and utilizing results solely for academic research purposes. My dedication to ethical research practices underscores the credibility and reliability of the study's outcomes, contributing to the advancement of knowledge in the field of electrical training and education.

Acknowledgments

The researcher wants to express his gratitude to his research adviser for his guidance and advice which led to the successful completion of the research. He is also grateful to his participants for their invaluable participation in the study for their evaluation of the trainer and their comments and suggestions for further improvement. He feels indebted to his loved ones, friends, and colleagues for their love and support.

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